

Kama Da Wane Ba Ta Wane: Matakan Rairaye Bincike Daga Ba Bincike Ba

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Citation: Sani, A-U. & Kurawa, H.M. (2023). Kama Da Wane Ba Ta Wane: Matakan Rairaye Bincike Daga Ba Bincike Ba. The Nasara Journal of Humanities, 11(1&2), 247-258. ISSN: 1118-6887.

Tsakure

Manufar wannan takarda ita ce nazartar matakan gano abin da yake ba bincike ba wanda da dama ake saka shi cikin sahan binciken ilimi. Binciken ya ginu kan salon bin kwakkwafi tare da kalailaice batutuwan da ake nazarta. Rubuce-rubucen ilimi da suka gabata masu alaƙa da wannan nazari su ne suka yi matashiya tare da samar masa da bayanana da yake bukata a matsayin majiya ko tushen bayanai na biyu. An dora aikin a Bahaushiyar hanyar gudanar da bincike ta "komai da mazauninsa." Hanyar ce kuma ta samar da hasashen cewa, rashin sanya abubuwa a muhallansu ke gurbata bincike. Binciken ya gano cewa, tasgaro a muhimman siffon ko matakan gudanarwa na kai ga bincike ya zama ba bincike ba. Daga karshe binciken ya ba da shawarar cewa ya kamata a samu hobbasar manyan makarantu da cibiyoyin bincike da ma masana da manazarta a matsayin daidaiƙu domin tabbatar da cewa wadanda abin ya shafa na bibiyar sababbin cigaba da ake samu a fannin binciken ilimi.

Fitilun Kalmomi: Bincike, Ba Bincike Ba, Matakai, Siffofi

1.0 Gabatarwa

Kalmar “bincike” sananniya ce da bakuna suka saba furtawa sannan kunnuwa suka saba ji a tsakanin Hausawa. Duk da haka, babban abin lura shi ne, an fi sanin ma’anar kalmar ne a bagiren yau da kullum, wato Hausar gama-gari. A muhallin ilimi, kalmar na da ma’ana ta musamman tare da waɗansu siffofi da nau’uka da mataakai. Binciken ilimi na buƙatar bayanai irin na ilimi da fasaha musamman saboda yadda lamuransa ke da sarkakiya da buƙatar fayyacewa. Misali, nau’in bincike shi ke nuni ga irin matakan da za a bi wajen gudanar da shi, sannan matakan ke ba wa binciken siffa ko a ce zubi da tsari. A ɗaya gefen kuwa, matakan da aka yi amfani da su wurin gudanar da bincike su ke nuni ga nau’in binciken.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, lamarin binciken ilimi abu ne da ke da girma da buƙatar zurfafa karatu da nazari. A har kullum manazarta da cibiyoyin bincike na ƙara fito da sababbin dabaru da hanyoyi da ƙa’idojin gudanar da bincike. Misali, fitacciyar hukumar nan ta *American Psychological Association* da aka fi sani da APA, na kan sabunta tsari da ƙa’idojin bincike musamman abin da ya shafi manazarta, lokaci zuwa lokaci.¹

Sau da dama bincike da aka gabatar a tarukan ƙara wa juna sani ko waɗanda aka tura domin bugawa a mujallun ilimi na fuskantar suka da ƙalubalen gazawa ta fuskar bin ƙa’idoji da amintaccen tsari. Haka ma abin yake a manyan makarantu yayin gabatar da kundayen digiri musamman a babban mataki. Masu gabatar da ƙudurin bincike ma na shan suka. Wani lokaci akan ayyana batu a matsayin wanda bai dace ba ko ba za a iya bincike a kansa ba (not researchable), ko kuma a bayyana shi a matsayin abin da ba bincike ba.² A bisa wannan, yana da kyau a samu rubuce-rubucen ilimi cikin harshen Hausa da za su ware zare da abawa game da bincike da abin da ba bincike ba. A bisa wannan ƙuduri ne aka gina wannan takarda domin (i) ƙara fito da abin da yake binciken ilimi fili da (ii) haska abin da yake ba bincike ba.

1.1 Dabarun gudanar da bincike

Wannan bincike an gina shi ne kan tsarin bayani na ƙwaƙƙwafi da ƙalailaice batutuwan da ake nazarta (descriptive survey). Duk bayanana da aka yi amfani da su sun kasance ƙarƙashin rukunin bayanai da aka samu daga majiya ta biyu (secondary source). Sannan an yi amfani da dabarar kwatanta bayanai da bin diddigin ingancin bayanai (musamman na kafonin da ba sanannu ba) domin tabbatar da inganci da amincin bayanana da aka samu.

¹ APA sun tabbatar da hakan a kan shafinsu. A APA, (2022 p. 1) an bayyana cewa sukan sabunta ƙa’idoji da bayanansu domin dacewa da sauye-sauyen ƙa’idoji da sababbin cigaba da ake samu a duniya.

² Wannan na da matuƙar alaƙa da batun binciken da mataakai da dabarun gudanar da shi.

Tussan bayanai (da suka kasance majiya ta biyu) da aka yi amfani da su sun hada da mujallu da bugaggun littattafai da kuma amintattun kafafen intanet ta fuskar samar da ingantattun bayanai, musamman na ilimi. Bayanan da aka tattara daga waɗannan tussa sun taimaka wajen haskaka muhimman batutuwan da ake nazarta daidai da jagorancin hanyar da aka dōra aikin. Daga karshe kuwa an kalailaice tare da kwankwance bayanan ta hanyar kwatantawa (comparison of information) da kuma fitar da sakayayyun bayanai ta la'akari da dalilai/abubuwan kamawa manya da kanana.

1.2 Ra'in bincike

Duk da cewa lamarin bincike abu ne da ya kasance game-duniya, wannan Bahaushen nazari ne. Dalilin zamowansa haka shi ne kasancewar manufarsa ya karkata kan ware abin da ya kasance binciken ilimi daga wanda yake ba bincike ba ta hanyar ba da karfi ga kadadar karatun Hausa. A bisa haka, an yi amfani da Bahaushiyar hanyar dōra aiki daidai da tunanin Bunza, (2019 p. 721) wanda duk da bai kore amfani da ra'o'in baren al'ummu ba, ya tafi kan cewa "a kowane irin al'amari gara a kai na hannu gida kafin a dawo a kama na dawa."³

An dōra wannan aikin kan tunanin Hausawa na "Komai da mazauninsa" (wai an dāura wa kuturu ankwa). A bisa wannan tunani, rashin bin matakan da suka dace yayin gudanar da bincike na iya samar da nafasu ga manufar da ake son cimmawa. Lura da wannan, takardar na da hasashen cewa, ta fuskar batu, akwai waɗanda suka kasance na binciken ilimi sannan akwai waɗanda ba na binciken ilimi ba. Haka kuma, rashin bin matakan binciken ilimi yadda ya kamata na iya sanya shi ya kasance ya zama ba bincike ba.

2.0 Bincike: Sigogi da matakansa

Sanin abu ciki da wajensa shi ne mataki na farko na kokarin fahimtar waninsa. Domin ware abin da yake ba bincike ba daga bincike, akwai bukatar sanin ma'ana da siffofin bincike tare da matakan da ake bi domin samar da shi. Wannan ɓangare na aikin zai mayar da hankali kan taliyon muhimman abubuwa da ke haɗuwa su samar da binciken ilimi.

³ A baya-bayan nan ana kara samun manazarta da ke amfani da falsafodin Hausawa a matsayin hanyoyin dōra aiki. Daga cikin rubuce-rubucen da aka dōra kan falsafodin Hausa a matsayin hanyar dōra aiki akwai Bunza, (2019) da Sani, Buba, & Mohammad, (2019) da Yahaya, (2020) da Sani & Jaja, (2020) da Shehu, (2022) da Sidi, (2023).

2.1 Ma'anar bincike

Kalmar "bincike" ta karafɛ rayuwar ɗan'adam ta yau da kullum. Kusan a kowane bagire ana amfani da ita ko kalmomi da ke zaman masu kinin ma'ana a gare ta.⁴ A bisa haka, kalmar na iya ɗaukar ma'anoni da dama masu makamanciyar ma'ana, amma mabambanta ta fuskar manufa da matakan aiwatarwa. Bunza, (2017 p. 22-23) ya kawo ma'anar binciken ilimi bayan nazartar jerin ma'anonin da manazarta daban-daban suka bayar. Ya ce:

Bibiyar diddigin wani abu ta hanyar taliyon mafarinsa da sabgoginsa da yanayeyanayensa. Bincike shi ne fito da wani abu sabo daga cikin abubuwan da aka sani ko ake gani ko ake ji ko ake amfani da su...

Shehu, (2018 p. 1) ya ba da ma'ana makamanciyar wannan inda yake cewa: "A ilimance, bincike na nufin aiwatar da nazari kan wani al'amari ko abu domin fito da wani sabon abu ko inganta wani abu, ko kuma warware wata matsala domin cimma wani buri ko biyan wata bukata."

Za a iya lura da cewa akwai muhimman kalmomi da ke haɗuwa su gina ma'anar bincike. Fahimtar su a matsayin ɗaiɗaikun kalmomi tare da fahimtar alakar aikin da suke yi kafada da kafada shi zai ba da hoton zuci na haƙikanin ma'anar binciken ilimi. Kalmomin kuwa su ne:

- i. Matsala
- ii. Manufa/makasudi
- iii. Matakai
- iv. Dabaru
- v. Bayanai
- vi. Kwankwancewa/kalailaicewa
- vii. Sakamako/Mafita

Lura da wannan, ana iya cewa binciken ilimi na nufin tunkarar wata matsala a ilimance cikin bin tsararrun matakai da dabaru bisa manufar tattara bayanai da bin ingantattun matakan tace su da kalailaice su don samun sakamako ko mafitar matsalar da ta haifar da makasudin gudanar da aikin.

⁴ A har kullum mutane na kan neman bayanai da suka shafi na zahiri da na baɗini. A kowace rana ba a rasa jin Hausawa sun ambaci kalmomi da ke da alaƙa da bincike (a bagiren yau-da-kullum) irin su "dubawa" ko "nema" ko "diddigi" ko "cigiya" da makamantansu. Bunza, (2017 p. 2) na ganin cewa ire-iren waɗannan kalmomi ne da suka kasance takwarorin kalmar "bincike."

2.1.2 Nau'ukan binciken ilimi

Lamarin binciken ilimi bai kasance nau'i guda kai tsaye ba. Yana da nau'uka daban-daban. Har ila yau, ya kasance abu mai sarkakiya wajen rarrabewa saboda yalwarsa da bangarorin ilimi da ya karade.⁵ Domin saukakawa da guje wa sarkakewar bayanai, ana iya samar da nau'ukan binciken ilimi a farkashin alkaluma mabambanta kamar haka:

1. Nau'ukan binciken ilimi ta fuskar tushen bayani: A nan ana la'akari da tushen bayanai da mai bincike ko masu bincike suka samo bayanai binciken. Sigogin bincike farkashin wannan nau'in su ne:

- i. Bincike daga majiya ta farko⁶
- ii. Bincike daga majiya ta biyu⁷

2. Nau'ukan binciken ilimi ta fuskar dalilin bincike: A nan akan yi la'akari da dalili ko matakin bincike ta fuskar lura da amfani ko tasirin da sakamakon bincike zai haifar. A farkashin wannan akan samu sigogin bincike kamar haka:

- i. Saukafakken bincike (basic research)⁸
- ii. Sarkafken bincike (applied research)⁹

3. Nau'ukan binciken ilimi ta fuskar fagen ilimi: Duk binciken ilimi da aka gudanar na fadawa farkashin daya daga cikin fagagen ilimi da ake da su. Akan kuma samu binciken da ya hada fagagen ilimi sama da guda.¹⁰ Manyan sigogin bincike da za a iya samu farkashin wannan rukuni su ne:

- i. Bincike a fannin fasaha (arts-based research)¹¹
- ii. Bincike a fannin kimiyya (science-based research)¹²

⁵ Domin farin bayani ana iya duba Johnson, & Christensen, (2004) da Creswell, (2015) da Kauru, (2015).

⁶ Akan tattara waɗannan bayanai kai tsaye daga tushe, waɗanda kuma bayanai sun kebanta ne ga binciken da ake gudanarwa. Misali, mai bincike na iya amfani da tambayau ko hira da makamantansu domin tattara bayanai game da tambayoyin biniken da yake gudanarwa.

⁷ Mai bincike ko masu bincike na samun bayanai ne daga majiya ta biyu, kamar littattafai, jaridu, muƙalu, da sauransu. Yana da kyau a lura cewa, majiya ta biyu na iya kasancewa majiya ta farko a wani nau'in bincike na daban. Misali, hotunan kan intanet na iya zama majiya ta farko ga mai bincike game da wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a kan intanet.

⁸ Wannan nau'in bincike ne mai saukin gudanarwa ta fuskar manufar da ake son cimma. Misali shi ne bincike domin gano sauye-sauye da farin ra'ayoyi da bunkasar fahimta a wani fagen ilimi - kamar a ce sababbin salailai a nazarin rubutaccen zuben Hausa.

⁹ Wannan bincike ne da ke mayar da hankali wajen samar da mafita ga matsaloli da ke faruwa. Misali na iya kasancewa bincike kan mafarin Boko Haram da matakan kawo farshen matsalar cikin sauki.

¹⁰ Misali, binciken Bunza, (2019) ya hada harshe da ilimin lissafi. Binciken Gobir & Sani (2019) kuwa ya shafi al'ada da addini.

¹¹ Misali, nazarin jigo da salon waƙoƙin baka.

¹² Misali, bincike a fagen kemistiri.

- iii. Bincike a fannin kimiyyar zamantakewa (social science-based research)¹³
- iv. Binciken gambizarar fagagen ilimi (multidisciplinary research)¹⁴

4. Rabe-Raben binciken ilimi ta fuskar nau'ukan bayanai: Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa wannan na da bambanci da "tushen bayanai" da aka yi bayani a farkashin "1" da ke kasan "2.1.2". Nau'in bayanai a nan ya shafi ire-iren bayanan da bincike ya kunsu. A farkashin wannan akwai:

- i. Binciken kididdiga (quantitative research)¹⁵
- ii. Binciken bayani (qualitative research)¹⁶

5. Rabe-Raben binciken ilimi ta fuskar nau'ukan hujjojin da sakamakon bincike ya dogara da su: Sigogin bincike sun bambanta idan aka yi la'akari da nau'ukan bayanan da ake kafa hujja da su a cikin binciken. Sannan da su ne ake gina sakamakon bincike.

- i. Nazarin bangarori/daidaikun alkaluma domin tabbatar da gama-gari/babban batu (inductive reasoning research)¹⁷
- ii. Kalailaice gama-garin alkaluma/babban batu domin bayanin bangarori/daidaikun alkaluma (deductive reasoning research)¹⁸

6. Nau'ukan binciken ilimi ta fuskar zurfin bincike: Bincike na bambanta ta fuskar zurfinsu. Yayin da waɗansu ke takaita kan farkarin gano ma'anonin batutuwa (concepts), waɗansu na shafar kwankwance batutuwa a muhallai mabambanta tare da bayanin dangantakarsu da waɗansu batutuwa na daban. Sigogin bincike farkashin wannan rukuni sun hada da:

- i. Nazartar batutuwa (exploratory)¹⁹
- ii. Bayanin batutuwa (descriptive)²⁰

¹³ Misali, bincike a fagen siyasa.

¹⁴ Misali, fito da tsattsafin likitanci daga rubutattun labaran Hausa.

¹⁵ Wannan sigar bincike ya fi shafar kididdigar lambobi. Ya shafi auna alkaluma ne domin tabbatarwa ko kore ra'o'i ko wata fahimtar da aka ginu a kanta.

¹⁶ Wannan ya fi shafar tattauna batutuwa. Ya shafi amfani da falsafa wajen kirkirowa ko bankado sababbin batutuwan ilimi ko kuma tattauna waɗanda ke wanzuwa domin kafawa ko bunkasa ra'o'i da fahimtoci da ake da su.

¹⁷ Nazarin da aka yi har ya kai ga sakamakon binciken da ke nuna tsarin karatun 6-3-3-4 shi ne mafita, misali ne na wannan sigar bincike.

¹⁸ Nazarin da ya nuna gazawar tsarin 6-3-3-4 (har aka kai ga samuwar 9-3-4), misali ne na wannan sigar bincike.

¹⁹ Ya ta'allafa ne kan farkarin fahimtar batutuwa kawai.

²⁰ Wannan ya shafi bayanin batutuwa. Ciki har da ma'anoninsu da nau'ukansu.

iii. Kalailaice batutuwa (explanatory)²¹

2.2 Siffofin bincike

Duk da cewa binciken ilimi na da nau'uka daban-daban, akwai waɗansu siffofi da ake samu a cikin kowane irin nau'in binciken ilimi. A nan siffar bincike na nufin tsari ko fasalin da bincike yake da shi. Ya kunshi tsarabe-tsarabensa da siffofinsa da suka bambance shi daga wani nau'in da ba shi ba. Za a iya lura da cewa, waɗannan siffofin bincike na da alaƙa irin ta saƙar saƙa. Wato dai, suna da dangantaka ta kai tsaye da juna yadda ɗauke guda daga ciki na iya jirkita daidaiton sauran. Binciken ilimi ya kunshi:

A. Matsala

Matsalar bincike jigo ne babba a kowane binciken ilimi. Ba a kafa harsashen wani bincike ba tare da samuwar matsala ba. A harshen binciken ilimi, matsalar bincike na nufin duk wani al'amarin da kasantuwar²² ce fashin bayan samuwar dalilin gudanar da bincike. Wato bai takaita ga ma'anar kalmar "matsala" a zancen yau da kullum ba. Hasali ma, matsalar bincike na iya kasancewa farin al'amari (al'amari mai kyau). Don haka, a saukafakken harshe ana iya cewa matsalar bincike na nufin abin da bincike ya damu da shi. A koyaushe yakan kasance babban ɓangare na dalilin gudanar da bincike.

Dangane da kasantuwar fari ko bakin al'amari a matsayin matsalar bincike, ana iya ɗaukar cin darasin Hausa a jarabawar kammala makarantun sakandare a matsayin misali. Koma baya ga cin jarabawar na iya kasancewa matsalar bincike a nazari mai take makamancin "Yawaitar Faɗuwa a Darasin Hausa a Jarabawar WAEC: Taliyon Sababi da Hasashen Mafita." Haka kuma, ƙaruwar cin darasin Hausar na iya kasancewa matsalar bincike a nazari mai take makamancin "Sabon Tsarin 6-3-3-4 da Karuwar Cin Darasin Hausa a Jarabawar WAEC."

B. Dalilin gudanarwa

Dalilin gudanar da bincike a harshen binciken ilimi na nufin abu ko abubuwan da suka sa mai bincike ko masu bincike ganin dacewa ko wajabin kafa harsashen bincike. Yana da alaƙa ta kai tsaye da matsalar bincike kasancewar a koyaushe matsalar bincike na daga cikin dalilan gudanar da shi. Waɗansu dalilan na daban na iya haɗawa da sha'awar

²¹ Wannan ya shafi kalailaice batutuwa da ya haɗa da ƙoƙarin kwanƙwance kalubalensu da guraben amfaninsu da sauran tsarabe-tsarabensu da dangantakarsu da sauran batutuwa.

²² Wanzuwar wani abu da ba a so ya wanzu ko ba a tsammanci ya wanzu ba na iya kasancewa matsalar bincike. Haka ma, rashin wanzuwar wani abu da ya kamata ya wanzu ko ake sa ran ya wanzu na iya kasancewa matsalar bincike.

manazarci a fannin, ko gogewarsa, ko tasirin matsalar binciken ga rayuwarsa ko al'ummarsa, da dai makamantansu.

C. Manufa da makasudi

Manufa da makasudi na tafiya ne a tare. Manufa na nufin dunkulallen bayani na kudurin da ake son cimmawa. Makasudi kuwa na nufin kebantattun bayanai na kai tsaye game da kudurin da ake son cimmawa wadanda ake iya auna mizanin nasararsu ko sabanin hakan.

Dukansu biyun na da alaka ta kai tsaye da matsalar bincike da kuma dalilin gudanarwa. Idan aka dauki misalin farko na taken da aka bayar a sakin layi na biyu farkashin A da ke kasan 2.2, ana iya samun manufa da makasudi kamar haka:

Manufa: ... binciko dalilan da ke haifar da karuwar faduwar darasin Hausa da daliban da ke rubuta jarabawar WAEC ke yi tare da nazartar ingantattun mataakai masu dorewa na magance matsalar.

Makasudi: (i) ... binciko dalilan da ke sa dalibai masu rubuta jarabawar WAEC faduwa darasin Hausa, (ii) ... binciko mataakai masu dorewa na magance matsalar faduwa darasin Hausa a jarabawar WAEC.

D. Dabarun gudanarwa

Dabarun gudanar da bincike na nufin duk wadansu tsararrun hanyoyi da mataakai da mai bincike ko masu bincike suka yi amfani da su domin ayyana kadadar bincikensu da tantance samfuransu da tattara bayanai da kalailaice su tare da fitar da sakamako ta la'akari da manya da kananan alƙaluma da ke cikin bayanai, duk bisa salon nazarin wani ayyanannen ra'i ko hanyar dora aiki.

Kowane binciken ilimi na gudanarwa ne da taimakon dabarun gudanarwa. Wannan ne ya sa dabarun bincike suke mazaunin wani muhimmin sifa na binciken ilimi. Su ma suna da alaka ta kai tsaye da sauran siffofi da aka zayyano a A da B da C da ke sama (duk farkashin 2.2). Misali, amfani da datattun ingantattun dabarun gudanar da bincike shi zai kai ga cimma manufar bincike.²³

E. Tattara bayanai

Hanyoyin tattara bayanai na nufin salo ko mataakai da dabarun da aka yi amfani da su wajen nemowa da tara bayanai da bincike ke hasashen nazartar su ne zai kai ga cimma

²³ Johnson & Christensen, (2004, p. 411-414) sun tattauna dabaru da hanyoyin gudanar da bincike.

manufar binciken da ake gudanarwa. Tattara bayanai siffa ce ta binciken ilimi inda ake bin waɗansu tsararrun matakan tattaro bayanai da ke da alaƙa da binciken.

Dabarun tattara bayanai da ake amfani da su na da alaƙa ta kai tsaye da siga ko nau'in binciken da ake gudanarwa. Akwai fitattun hanyoyin tattara bayanai da dama. Sun haɗa da tambayau da kurulla/sanya ido da hira, da sauran makamantan waɗannan.²⁴

F. Kalailaice bayanai

Kalailaice bayanai na nufin kwankwance bayanai ta hanyar nazartar dukkannin alƙaluma manya da kanana da ke cikinsu da lura da dangantaka da bambancin da ke tsakanin bangarorin bayanan domin hasashen inganci ko rauninsu da tasirin bangarorin a matsayin daidaiƙunsu ko yayin da suke bagiren haɗaka a kan yanayi na gama-gari ko keɓantacce, duk bisa zurfaffan falsafa, karkashin jagorancin ra'i ko hanyar dora bincike. Wannan mataki shi ne zai kai ga fitar da sakamakon binciken da ake gudanarwa.²⁵

G. Sakamako

Kafin bincike ya kammala, dole sai an fitar da sakamakonsa. Sakamakon bincike na nufin abubuwan da aka gano bayan kalailaice bayanan binciken waɗanda ke da alaƙa da matsalar bincike, waɗanda kuma su za su nuna canjaras ko sabanin hasashen bincike tare da bayyana nasarar makasudin bincike ko sabanin hakan.²⁶

H. Manazarta

Mai binciken ilimi ba ya kulle kansa a daki domin gudanarwa. Dole akwai gabataccen ilimi da ya yi tasiri a cikin binciken ko dai kai tsaye ko a kaikaice. Manazarta sifa ce ta binciken ilimi.²⁷

I. Harshen bincike

Harshen binciken ilimi ya bambanta da zance na yau da kullum. Harshen bincike na nufin tsarariyar hanyar zaɓen kalmomi da jeranta su a gurabun da suka dace bisa sani da bin shatacciyar ƙa'ida. Harshen bincike ba ya amfani da kalamai na kuɗin goro (overgeneralization) ko kokonto ko mayar da zance ga manazarci, da makamantansu.²⁸

²⁴ A duba Sonmez, (2018 p. 2601) domin samun ƙarin bayani game da hanyoyin tattara bayanai.

²⁵ Charles, (2016 p. 14) ya kawo bayanai game da hanyoyin kalailaice bayanai.

²⁶ Rubuce-rubucen Livingston, (2012) da na Kabir, (2016) na dāuke da bayanai game da.

²⁷ Domin ƙarin bayani game da manazarta ana iya duba Shibly, (2016) ko University of Otago. (2017).

²⁸ Domin ƙarin bayani game da harshen bincike, ana iya duba Strongman, (2013) da Al-Shaibani, (2016).

2.3 Matakan gudanar da bincike

Kowane binciken ilimi na da matakan gudanarwa na musamman. Matakan gudanar da bincike na nufin tsararrun gaɓoɓi da kowannensu ke mazaunin muhimmin mataki da mai bincike ko masu bincike ke aiwatar da wani abu na musamman a cikinsa. Matakan gudanar da bincike na da dangantaka ta kai tsaye da sigar binciken da za a gudanar.

Manazarta da cibiyoyin bincike da daban-daban sun yi tsokaci game da matakan gudanar da binciken ilimi. Daga cikinsu akwai Online Library Learning Center (n.d. p. 1) da Charles, (2016 p. 15-21) da University of Michigan. (2017 p. 5) da sauransu. Bayan nazartar bayanan manazarta daban-daban, wannan takarda ta fahimci cewa akwai muhimman matakan gudanar da bincike kamar haka:

- A. Fitar da tambayar bincike: Wato ayyana tambayoyin da bincike ke son amsawa. Samun amsoshin tambayoyin na daidai da cimma manufar binciken.
- B. Tattara bayanai: Wannan ne zai sa a samu karin haske game da muhimman batutuwa da ke cikin binciken. Tattara bayanai a wannan gaɓar ya haɗa da bitar ayyukan da suka gabata.
- C. Daidaita batun bincike: Bayanan da aka samu a mataki na B da ke sama (karkashin 2.3) shi zai taimaka wajen fara daidaita batun binciken. A wannan gaɓar an samu karin haske game da batun ta yadda za a fara daidaita shi.
- D. Yin la'akari da kayan aikin da ake da su: Kayan aiki a nan sun funshi duk abubuwan da haɗakarsu ne zai kai ga an samu nasarar gudanar da binciken. Ciki har da lokaci da kuɗaɗe da ake buƙata da kayayyakin gwaje-gwaje da sauransu.
- E. Zaɓen dabarun bincike da suka fi dacewa: Za a yi hakan ne ta la'akari da sigar binciken da za a gudanar.
- F. Bin dabarun binciken: Wannan ya haɗa da aiki da ra'i da dabarun tattara bayanai da na kwankwance su da makamantansu.
- G. Tattara bayanai
- H. Kalailaice bayanai
- I. Tsara rubutu/rahoton bincike: Tsara rahoton zai sa ya fito cikin sifar binciken ilimi kamar yadda aka yi bayani a karkashin 2.2 da ke sama.
- J. Tsara manazarta

3.0 Ba Bincike Ba

A wannan gaɓa, kai tsaye za a iya cewa abin da ba bincike ba shi ne wanda ya ci karo ko ya gaza cike mizanai da aka zayyano a karkashin 2.1 da 2.2 da 2.3 da ke sama. Akan samu

rubuce-rubuce da aka yi kai tsaye, wadanda ba a yi su da sunan binciken ilimi ba.²⁹ A daya bangaren kuma, ana iya samar da tsararren rubutu bisa ka'idoji da kyakkyawan zubi da da tsari, amma ya gaza amsa sunan binciken ilimi kasancewar ba a dora shi kan alkaluman bincike da suka dace ba.

Yayin da marubuci ko marubuta suka kuduri aniyar gudanar da binciken ilimi, akwai abubuwa daban-daban da ka iya samar da komabaya ga yunkurinsu. Wannan takarda za ta tattauna su cikin manyan rukunoni guda biyu (a farkashin 3.1 da 3.2 da ke kasa) kamar haka:

- a. Gazawa ta fuskar sifa
- b. Gazawa ta fuskar mata kai

3.1 Ba bincike ba ta sifa

Basana da manazarta da dama sun kawo bayanai da suka shafi abin da ba bincike ba ta la'akari da alkaluma daban-daban.³⁰ Wannan takarda ta zaɓi bin falsafar tatso bayanai daga gama-garin alkaluma/babban batu domin bayanin bangarori/daidaikun alkaluma (deductive reasoning). An yi hakan bisa jagorancin hanyar dora binciken tare da yakinin cewa cikakkiyar fahimtar abin da yake bincike, shi zai kai ga gano abin da yake waninsa kai tsaye.

A farkashin 2.2 da ke sama, an kawo waɗansu fitattun siffon binciken ilimi guda tara (9) (A – I). Ko da manazarci ko manazarta sun kuduri niyyar gudanar da binciken ilimi, rauni a daya ko sama daga cikin waɗannan siffon bincike na iya zare nazarin nasu daga sahan binciken ilimi. A kasa an kawo misalan yadda ire-iren rauni da za a iya samu a siffon bincike ka iya zamar da rubutu ba bincike ba.

A. Matsala da dalilin gudanarwa

Dole a samu dalilin gudanar da bincike kafin kafa harsashensa. Shi kuwa dalilin bincike kai tsaye na da alaƙa da matsalar binciken. Rubutun da aka yi ba tare da samuwar wata matsala da dalilin gudanar da shi ba, ba za a kira shi bincike ba. Dole ne bincike ya bayyana matsala da dalilin gudanar da shi farara.

B. Manufa da makasudi

Idan babu manufa, lallai babu binciken ilimi. Idan aka samar da aiki ba tare da manufa ba, kai tsaye ba za a tsammaci sakamakon bincike ba da ke nuna an samo mafita ko amsa

²⁹ Misalan waɗannan sun haɗa da rubutun kagaggen labari, rubutun labaran tafiye-tafiye da mutum ya yi, ko rubuta waƙa mai jigon da ba ya buƙatar bincike na musamman, da makamantansu.

³⁰ Bunza, (2017 p. 17) ya kawo misalan abubuwan da ba bincike ba guda 11.

game da matsalar bincike ko sabanin hakan. Wanda ya kafa alkalami ba tare da manufa da mafasudin rubutunsa ba, to ba zai kira abin da ya yi bincike ba.

C. Dabarun gudanarwa: A farkashin D da ke kasan 2.2 a sama, an yi bayanin dabarun gudanar da bincike. Sun kasance wajibi a cikin binciken ilimi. Binciken da aka gudanar kara zube ba tare da tsararrun dabaru ba, yana da nakasu matuƙa, sannan yana iya zama ba bincike ba.

D. Kalailaice bayanai: Yayin da marubuci ko marubuta suka tattaro ma'anonin kalmomi daga litattattafai ko kamusoshi, to abin da suka yi ba bincike ba ne. Kafin a kira shi bincike, dole ne ya samu cikakkiyar siffar kalailaice bayanai da aka tattauna a farkashin F, a kasan 2.2. Kalailaice bayanai zai shafi kwatanta batutuwan bisa tsararriyar falsafa tare da fofarin tatso sababbin muhamman bayanai daga gare su.

E. Sakamako: Kai tsaye binciken da ba shi da sakamako ya zama ba bincike ba domin babu yadda za a yi ya cimma manufarsa. Idan a farkashen bincike ba a fitar da sakamako ba, daidai yake da ba a gudanar da binciken ba gaba daya. Sakamakon shi ne zai kai ga samar da mafita ga matsalar bincike.

F. Manazarta: Dauko ayyukan mutane ba tare da bayyana tushen binciken ba tare da sanya kyakkyawar manazarta na iya sawa bincike ya zama mai rauni ko ma ya tashi daga sahan binciken ilimi. Ko da an sanya tushen bincike, kwashe-kwashe sama da kima da ya saɓa wa wanzajjiyar fa'idar manazarta na iya sa rubutu ya zama ba bincike ba.

G. Harshen bincike: Rashin amfani da harshen bincike nakasu ne ga binciken ilimi. Misalan kauce wa harshen bincike sun hada da:

- i. Kokonto: Misalan kalamai da ke nuna kokonto sun hada da "ana ganin cewa", "wataƙila", "ana tunanin cewa" da makamantansu.³¹
- ii. Kudin goro (overgeneralization): Akwai batutuwa da suka kasance na gama-gari, kamar fitowar rana ta gabas ko cewar duk wani mai rai mamaci ne. A ɓangare guda, saɓawa binciken ilimi ne yin kudin goro ga al'amarin da ake kila-wa-kalar kasancewarsa na gama-garin. Misalan wannan na iya kasancewa "babu wani dan Afirka da bai taɓa jin labarin Hausawa ba", "babu kasar da ba za a samu Bahaushe ba" da makamantansu.
- iii. Mayar da zance zuwa ga kai: Misalan kalamai da ke nuna manazarci na mayar da zance zuwa ga kansa sun hada da "na fahimci cewa", "na gano cewa", "an sanar da ni cewa" da makamantansu.

³¹ Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, akwai gurabun da waɗannan misalai ba za su fito a matsayin kokonto da ake magana a kai ba.

- iv. Takama: Misalan harshen takama sun haɗa da “fage ne da na nakalta”, “na fware a wannan fannin” da makamantansu.

3.2 Ba bincike ba ta mataki

A farkashin 2.3 an zayyano waɗansu fitattun matakan gudanar da bincike guda goma (A – J). Tsallake wani mataki ko waɗansu matakai da suke wajibi ga binciken da aka kudurta gudanarwa na samar da nakasu ga bincike ko ma ya mayar da shi ba bincike ba. Wannan ya danganta da matakin da aka kuskure ko aka gaza bin sa a kammale.

Kai tsaye nazarin da aka fara ba tare da ayyana tambayoyin da ake buƙata binciken ya amsa ba (dalilin gudanar da bincike), ya kasance ba binciken ilimi ba. Haka kuma, bincike ba zai gudana ba har sai an tattara bayanai da ke da nasaba da binciken. Tsallake wannan mataki na nufin babu bayanan da za a kalailaice domin fitar da sakamakon bincike.

Rashin la’akari da kayan aikin da ake da su kuwa na sa a kafa harsashen binciken da mai bincike ko masu bincike ba su da damar kammalawa. Irin wannan yanayi na iya kai ga an yi watsi da bincike ko kuma an kammala shi cikin siga marar inganci da aminci wanda hakan zai zamar da shi ba bincike ba. Haka ma abin yake ga zaɓen dabarun bincike da suka fi dacewa da gudanar da shi. Misali, yin amfani da tambayau (questionnaire) ga samfurin jama’ar bincike (research population sample) da ba su iya karatu da rubutu ba na iya haifar da nakasu kai tsaye.

Idan aka tattara bayanai aka zube su ba tare da kwankwancewa ba, hakan bai zama bincike ba. Dole ne a kalailaice su domin fitar da sakamako. Haka kuma, kafin bincike ya cika, dole sai an tsaro shi a rubuce.³² Ko da an kammala waɗannan gaba ɗaya, har ila yau bincike ba ya amsa sunansa har sai an samu tsararriyar manazarta.

4.0 Sakamakon bincike

Binciken ilimi fage ne mai faɗi da a har kullum masana da manazarta ke ci gaba da rubuce-rubuce game da lamura daban-daban da suka shafe shi. Wanda ya yi sake wajen bibiyar cigaba da ake samu a wannan fagen ilimi na iya kasancewa ana ga doki yana ga fura. Dalili kuwa shi ne, zai yi ta sanya abubuwa ba a muhallansu ba sakamakon bin tsohon tsari wanda sababbin nazarce-nazarce suka shafe shi. Sanya abubuwa ba a mazaunansu ba kuwa na iya sakawa aikin ma’aikacin ya kasance ba bincike ba.

Masana da manazarta daban-daban sun yi rubuce-rubuce da ke nuna cewa akwai abubuwan da ke sa bincike ya zama ba bincike ba (kamar yadda aka bayyana a farkashin 3.0 da ke sama). Dalilan da ke haifar da rauni ga inganci da amincin bincike na da yawa.

³² Bayan rubuta shi ana iya mayar da shi odiyo ko bidiyo.

Sanin mene ne bincike zai taimaka wajen gane duk abin da ba a sanya shi a mazauninsa, wanda hakan na iya zamar da shi ba bincike ba.

Ana iya nazartar abubuwan da ke sa nazari ya kasance ba bincike ba a farkashin siffofi da matakan gudanar da bincike. Kamar yadda aka kawo a farkashin A – G da ke kasan 3.1, yayin da nazari ya rasa cikakkun siffofin bincike, ko ya samu tasgaro a wani ko wadansu daga ciki, to zai kasance ya samu rauni. Haka abin yake yayin da aka kuskure matakan gudanarwa kamar yadda aka kawo a farkashin 3.2.

Domin kauce wa wannan matsala, akwai bukatar tarukan fara wa juna sani da laccoci da za su wayar da kai game da muhimmanci da wajibcin bibiyar sababbin sauye-sauye (new trends) da ake samu a bangaren bincike da nazari. Ga dalibai kuwa, akwai bukatar jaddadawa da faɗaɗa batun “ba bincike ba” a cikin kwasa-kwasan da suka shafi koyar da bincike. Haka kuma, akwai bukatar jami’o’i da kwaleji-kwaleji da cibiyoyin bincike da su riƙa samar da takardu masu bayanin sababbin sauye-sauye a fannin bincike cikin saukakakken harshe, kamar dai yadda manyan jami’o’i da cibiyoyin bincike a duniya ke yi.³³ Ana iya dora waɗannan takardu a kafafen intanet ɗin manyan makarantu da laburare da cibiyoyin bincike domin saukafa samu.

4.1 Kammalawa

Karuwar ilimi da bunkasar sababbin fasahohin bincike na sa har kullum ana fito da sababbin sigogi da matakan gudanar da binciken ilimi. Sauye-sauye da ake samu a fa’idoji da matakan gudanar da bincike na bukatar manazarta da marubuta da daliban ilimi su himmatu wurin bibiyar sababbin cigaba da ake samu a wannan fanni. Hakan ne kadai zai tabbatar da ba a bar su a baya ba. Hakan zai tabbatu ne da taimakon manyan makarantu da cibiyoyin bincike. A fagen bincike, da muguwar rawa gwara kin tashi, domin sakamakon bincike marar inganci da aminci na iya kasance mai batarwa da illatarwa ta hanyoyi mabambanta.

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